

Development and Application of a Relational Database of Crustal Models in Italy

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Executive Summary

Crustal-scale models are a fundamental resource for investigating the structure and physical properties of the Earth's outer shell, as well as for supporting a wide range of geophysical and geological applications, including earthquake hazard analyses, tectonic interpretation, and geodynamic modeling. However, information on crustal structure is often fragmented across heterogeneous sources, described using non-standardized formats, and is difficult to compare or reuse systematically.

The aim of this work is to develop an open and structured database of crustal models, with a focus on the Italian region. The database is constructed by compiling crustal-scale models from the scientific literature and existing public repositories, integrating information derived from various methodologies, spatial scales, and parameterizations. Rather than generating new models, this effort focuses on harmonizing, normalizing, and organizing previously published data within a coherent and transparent framework.

Each model is documented through elementary metadata, spatial references, and a set of normalized attributes that describe its geometry, physical properties, and methodological assumptions. The resulting database enables direct comparison among models, facilitates spatial analyses, and supports data reuse in interdisciplinary studies. By providing a consolidated and extensible repository, this initiative represents a step toward improving accessibility, consistency, and long-term usability of crustal modeling information for the Italian territory (our starting region) and beyond.

1. Methods, data selection, and database structure

1.1 Methods

The database is constructed using crustal-scale models derived primarily from the scientific literature, publicly available national and international databases, and supplementary materials associated with published studies. The parameters of interest are the P-wave velocity, S-wave velocity, and density. Only models with sufficient documentation to allow spatial referencing and interpretation of key parameters are included. The scientific content of the original models is preserved, while their representation is standardized, including unit conversions and map geographic system reference, to ensure consistency across the database.

Models are selected based on their relevance to the Italian territory and surrounding regions, the availability of spatial information defining the model's extent, and the clarity of the methodological description and parameter definition. When multiple versions or updates of a model are available, the most recent or complete version is included preferentially, with links to related records when applicable, or at the very least, ensuring that both versions are maintained.

To effectively incorporate these data into the database, it is necessary to ensure that they are spatially discretized for the specific areas (i.e., cells) or sections selected. If the data is already discretized, those values can be used directly in the database, preserving the original discretization. However, if the data is not discretized (e.g., the model is available only as a raster image), the necessary discretization will be performed based on the model's features to capture the most significant changes in the parameter values within the model's spatial extent

1.2 Data selection

For the construction of the present database, a selection of crustal-scale models providing geological and geophysical information for the study area has been considered. Most of the included models are from tomographic studies. The database includes models covering the Calabrian Arc (Pondevivo & Panza, 2006), the Central-Eastern Alpine sector (Scarascia & Cassinis, 1997), the Northern Apennines (Cassinis et al., 2003), and the Central–Southern Apennines (Improta et al., 2003). Furthermore, two major volcanic areas are specifically addressed: the Campi Flegrei caldera and the Etna volcanic region. For these latter areas, the database incorporates crustal models routinely used in the seismic monitoring and analysis activities of the INGV Osservatorio Vesuviano (Campi Flegrei) and the INGV Osservatorio Etneo (Etna).

In some cases, model parameters are provided as spatially distributed values defined over areal cells or grids, whereas in other cases, information is extracted or reported along geological or geophysical cross-sections. These different data representations are explicitly accounted for during the normalization process and are illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1 – Maps showing the data analyzed in this work. Polygons indicate areas for which model parameters are available in the literature as spatially distributed values defined over cells or areal domains. Line segments represent geological or geophysical cross-sections extracted from published studies, along which crustal parameters have been digitized and used to populate the database.

1.3 Relational structure of the models

The database is structured to ensure standardized representation, interoperability, and ease of analysis of crustal-scale models across the Italian region. Each model is assigned a unique identifier and is associated with metadata describing its source, spatial extent, methodological approach, and reference publication.

The geophysical parameters considered for each model include, when present, the depth of the crustal layers, P-wave velocity (V_p), S-wave velocity (V_s), and density (Rho).

These parameters are systematically recorded for each geological or geophysical medium represented in the model, whether the original data are provided as areal distributions over cells or extracted along cross-sections.

The database is implemented using a relational structure comprising:

1. Model Table – provides a concise description of each model, including its name, the methodology used to derive the four main geophysical parameters, and other relevant metadata such as spatial coverage and reference source. This table links directly to both the feature and attribute tables, providing a comprehensive overview of the dataset contents.
2. Feature Table – contains spatial representations of the models, including polygons for areal domains and line segments for cross-sections. Each spatial feature is linked to a unique model identifier.
3. Attribute Table – stores the numerical and descriptive properties of the crustal layers, including the geophysical parameters (depth, V_p , V_s , ρ) for each layer or segment. Each record in the attribute table is associated with a feature from the feature table, ensuring traceability and enabling spatial queries.

Table 1. Model Table

Field name	Type	Description
IDModel	string	Unique identification code of the model
ModelName	string	Name of the model as reported in the literature
VpMethod	string	Method used to determine P-wave (V_p) velocity
VsMethod	string	Method used to determine S-wave (V_s) velocity
DensityMethod	string	Method used to determine density (ρ)

Table 2. Feature Table

Field name	Type	Description	Units
IDModel	string	Unique identification code of the model	-
NameFeature	string	Name of the feature	-
IDFeature	integer	Unique identification code of the feature	-
DataType	string	Type of data based on geometry: L=line, A=area	-
Lat1	float	L: latitude of line start; A: latitude of upper-west corner of bounding box	degrees
Lon1	float	L: longitude of line start; A: longitude of upper-west corner of bounding box	degrees
Lat2	float	L: latitude of line end; A: latitude of lower-east corner of bounding box	degrees
Lon2	float	L: longitude of line end; A: longitude of lower-east corner of bounding box	degrees
Size	float	P: always 0; L: line length; A: diagonal length of bounding box	km

Table 3. Attribute Table

Field name	Type	Description	Units
IDModel	string	Unique identification code of the model	-
NameFeature	string	Name of the feature	-
IDFeature	integer	Unique identification code of the feature	-
LayerName	string	Name of the layer	-
DepthMax	float	Maximum depth of the layer or depth of the lower edge from sea level	km
Thickness	float	Thickness of the layer	km
Vp	float	P-wave (primary wave) velocity	km/s
Vs	float	S-wave (secondary wave) velocity	km/s
Density	float	Density of the layer	g/cm ³

1.4. Database Structure and Access for Crustal Models

The database is designed to provide both a high-level overview and full access to the detailed geophysical parameters for each crustal model. For every model, a master table is included (see **Table 4**), which summarizes the key characteristics of the model, including maximum depth, number of layers, and the available geophysical parameters (Vp, Vs, and density). This master table is linked to the spatial features representing the model, allowing

users to click on a geographic feature—either a polygon for areal data or a line segment for cross-section data—and immediately view the model-level summary.

In addition to the master table, a comprehensive full data table is provided (see Table 5). This table contains all detailed layer-by-layer information for the selected model, corresponding to the entries in the attribute table. After interacting with a spatial feature and reviewing the summary in the master table, users can access the full dataset through a dedicated link that directs them to the complete table for that specific model.

This integrated structure ensures seamless navigation between spatial visualization, model summary, and complete data access. Users can rapidly explore the general characteristics of the models while retaining the ability to download and analyze the full set of geophysical parameters, facilitating reproducible research and detailed scientific investigations.

Table 4. Master table

Field name	Type	Description
VelocityModel	string	Unique identifier for the velocity model
NumStrata	integer	Number of crustal layers in the model
NumCellsSections	integer	Number of spatial units: cells for areal data, sections for cross-section data
DataType	string	Type of data: A = areal (cells), S = cross-section (lines)
Vp Model	string	Indicates whether P-wave velocity (Vp) is included in the model (Y/N)
Vs Model	string	Indicates whether S-wave velocity (Vs) is included in the model (Y/N)
Rho Model	string	Indicates whether density (ρ) is included in the model (Y/N)
Reference	string	Source or reference of the model
Link	string	URL link to the source or supporting documentation

2. Models Included in the Database

2.1 Model Selection Criteria

The crustal models included in the database were selected to ensure broad coverage of the Italian territory while maintaining consistency and usability. The study areas span, from north to south, the Central-Eastern Alpine sector, the Northern Apennines, the Central and Southern Apennines, the Calabrian Arc, the Campi Flegrei, and the Etna volcanic region. These zones collectively explore a large spatial extent of the entire Italian peninsula.

The type of data differs depending on the region. For the Calabrian Arc, the data are primarily areal, represented over cells to capture spatial variability within the area. For the

remainder of the country, including the Apennines and Alpine sectors, as well as the volcanic areas of Campi Flegrei and Etna, the data are primarily derived from cross-sections, reflecting the geophysical information available in the literature and previous studies.

It is essential to note that not all models encompass the complete set of geophysical parameters considered for the database. Each model may provide a subset of the chosen parameters—maximum and minimum depth, layer thickness, P-wave velocity (V_p), S-wave velocity (V_s), and density (ρ)—depending on data availability and the methodology of the original study.

This selection strategy ensures that the database captures a representative view of the crustal structure across Italy, allowing for integration, comparison, and subsequent analysis while transparently reporting the presence or absence of specific parameters for each model.

2.2 List of Models and Main Characteristics

Table 6 integrates the main “master tables” and summarizes the key attributes of each model considered in the database.

Table 5 – Models currently included in the database

Velocity Model	NumStrata	Num Elements	Data Type	Vp Model	Vs Model	Rho Model	Reference	Link
CAM01	7	1	A	Y	Y	N	Sala Sismica OV-INGV	https://www.ov.ingv.it/
SIC01	7	1	A	Y	Y	N	Sala Sismica OE-INGV	https://www.ct.ingv.it/
CAL01	9	8	A	N	Y	N	2278	https://doi.org/10.1007/s00024-006-0093-3
CAL02	6	16	S	Y	N	N	3199	https://pubs.geoscienceworld.org/sgf/italianjgeo/article/122/3/365/74857/The-deep-crustal-structure-of-Italy-and
CEN20	5	10	S	Y	N	Y	3433	https://doi.org/10.1016/S0040-1951(99)00267-X
CEN21	5	11	S	Y	N	N	3199	https://pubs.geoscienceworld.org/sgf/italianjgeo/article/122/3/365/74857/The-deep-crustal-structure-of-Italy-and
CEN22	12	27	S	Y	N	N	1576	https://doi.org/10.1016/S0040-1951(96)00206-5

3. The Downloadable Master Table

3.1 Structure of the Master Table

The downloadable master table provides users with full access to the complete set of crustal parameters for each velocity model included in the database. After selecting a geographic feature corresponding to a specific model (whether an area for areal data or a line for cross-sectional data), the user is redirected to the master table via a dedicated link.

For each model, a full table is provided for each parameter (V_p , V_s , and density), where values are organized per individual crustal layer. The tables include the depth and the corresponding parameter values for all layers, allowing a detailed inspection of the vertical structure of the crust (**Appendix**).

For instance, in the V_p full table, each row represents a specific cell or section of the model (Cells/Sections), while the columns ($VP1$, $VP2$, ...) correspond to the successive crustal layers of the model. This structure allows users to quickly compare the layer-by-layer properties across multiple models. Some cells may remain empty where data for a specific layer or parameter is not available, reflecting the heterogeneous nature of the compiled datasets.

The table format is flexible and uniform across all parameters, enabling easy integration with visualization and analysis tools. Users can download the table in standard formats (e.g., CSV or Excel) for further processing, modeling, or integration into other geoscientific applications.

This structure ensures that each feature, once selected, provides direct access to the complete set of depth-dependent parameters for the corresponding model, allowing both rapid overview and detailed quantitative analysis of the Italian crustal models.

4. Final remarks

The crustal velocity database presented in this report provides a comprehensive and structured compilation of geophysical parameters for the Italian territory, covering key regions from the Central Eastern Alpine sector, the Northern and Central-Southern Apennines, the Calabrian Arc, to the Campi Flegrei and Etna areas. Data for areal models, such as the Calabrian Arc, are organized in spatial cells, while data for other regions are provided along cross-sectional lines.

For each velocity model, the database includes depth-dependent parameters (P-wave velocity, S-wave velocity, and density) for individual crustal layers, organized in master tables and downloadable full tables. Not all parameters are available for every model, reflecting the heterogeneous nature of the literature and observational sources used.

This dataset is designed to support both scientific research and applied geophysical analyses, providing an accessible resource for studying the structure of the Italian crust. Its

interactive design links geographic features to detailed parameter tables, allowing users to easily explore, download, and utilize the data for modeling, visualization, or integration with other geoscientific datasets.

The release of the database in OGC standard web services (WFS) is under consideration.

Future expansions of the database may include additional crustal models, enhanced spatial resolution, and supplementary geophysical parameters, which would further increase its value as a reference tool for the geoscience community.

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